

SUPERHYDROPHOBIC COATINGS FOR ENHANCED FIBRE COMPOSITE MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Manufacturing of fiber reinforced composite materials have seen a tremendous growth in the last few decades attributable to their improved properties over their constituent matrix and fiber materials, resulting in their widespread application. This increased usage has brought forward some scarcely studied issues of such materials. In this research work, we try to address one such challenge of moisture degradation of composite materials. Three different carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites: poly ether ether ketone, polyamide 6 and epoxy were coated with polyurethane poly (methyl methacrylate) interpenetrating polymer network and fluoro silica forming a micro-nano textured surface imparting superhydrophobic properties to these substrates which were then kept immersed in water for one day along with uncoated samples to study moisture degradation. Substrates covered with superhydrophobic coatings demonstrated 21-60% reduced water absorption as compared to their uncoated counterparts.

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite materials possess superior properties compared to their constituent matrix and reinforcement materials enabling their deployment in numerous modern applications. Generally, composite materials showcase excellent mechanical properties such as high strength while simultaneously allowing for significant weight reductions. This makes them an attractive option for manufacturing despite their higher costs and have already found extensive use in naval structures, sporting gear, aircraft components, modern automotive construction and biomedical parts to name a few [1]–[7]. Although composite materials like carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) and glass fibre reinforced polymer (GFRP) are being used to manufacture several industrial parts and components, they are far from being a perfect material. One notable disadvantage is the deleterious effect of moisture on the mechanical and thermal properties of composite materials [8]–[12]. As humidity is an inevitable form of environmental exposure, moisture induced degradation is a common problem which needs to be overcome to fabricate durable fibre reinforced composites.

An example of such degradation can be observed in carbon fibre epoxy (CF-epoxy) and GFRP composites [11], [13]. CF-epoxy after moisture absorption experiences decreased fracture strength by almost 66%, reduced compressive strength between 23-37%, upto 42% reduced stiffness and 41% decrease in its glass transition temperature (T_g). Similarly, flexure modulus of GFRP is reduced to half when exposed to water. Uptake of water for glass fibres can be considerably more than carbon fibres due to the presence of hydroxyl and other polar groups on the surface of the glass fibres. The degradation in these fibres begin when ions are extracted out of the glass fibres by water which then form a basic solution leading to further degradation of the composite. However, in both carbon and

glass fibres the predominant affect for occurrence of degradation is the weakening of matrix-fibre interface on exposure to moisture. Composites with higher matrix content are affected the most.

In this study, we try to address this moisture degradation problem by imparting superhydrophobic characteristics to composite materials. Superhydrophobic coatings rely on the formation of nano-micro textured pattern on the surface of a substrate forming low surface energy interface leading to the Cassie-Baxter state [14]. The higher surface energy water droplet forms a contact angle of greater than 150° and a roll-off angle of less than 10° with this comparatively low surface energy micro-nano hierarchically generated rough surface. Artificially fabricated superhydrophobic coatings have long been known to surpass the performance of naturally occurring self-cleaning surfaces like lotus leaf [15] in terms of contact and roll-off angle, but these have until now generated interest in the study of moisture resistant effects on paper, fabric, wood and cementitious composites [16]–[20]. In our research, we were not able to find any studies that demonstrate the feasibility of fabricating superhydrophobic fibre reinforced composites for avoiding moisture degradation and improving composite properties.

Fluorinated silica nanoparticles have been widely used for providing contact angles greater than 150° but its application is severely restricted due to its poor mechanical durability. In a previous study, our team has shown the enhanced performance of superhydrophobic coatings on various substrates like glass, aluminum, and claystone when fluoro silica (FSiO_2) layer is preceded by a polyurethane (PU) poly (methyl methacrylate) (PMMA) interpenetrating polymer network (IPN) coating [21]. As opposed to polymer blends, which are mixtures of two or more polymers, IPNs are networks of two or more polymers interlaced at the molecular level without forming any covalent bonds amongst themselves. This makes them one of the toughest class of polymers with applications being considered in the fabrication of bullet proof glass [22]. Herein, we extend this study to coat some of the most commonly encountered high-performance fibre reinforced composites: carbon fibre polyether ether ketone (CF-PEEK), CF-epoxy and carbon fibre polyamide 6 (CF-nylon) to test for their moisture resistance after forming a superhydrophobic layer.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Synthesis of PU PMMA IPN

A two-pot synthesis method is used to prepare acrylic and urethane components separately before carrying out simultaneous polymerization to form the IPN. Acrylic mixture is first prepared by the addition of 40 mL acetone (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99.5\%$) in a 50 mL falcon tube (pot A). To this 2.02 mL of methyl methacrylate (Sigma-Aldrich, 99%) (MMA) is added followed by 94.4 μL of trimethylolpropane trimethacrylate (Sigma-Aldrich, 90%) (TRIM) and 60.8 μL of 2,2'-azobis(2-methylpropionitrile) solution (Sigma-Aldrich, 0.2 M in toluene) (AIBN). Similarly, 40 mL xylene (Univar, 99%) is added to a 125 ml schott glass bottle (pot B). To this 0.44 g of 1,1,1-tris(hydroxymethyl)propane (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 98\%$) (TRIOH) is added followed by vigorous stirring at 1000 rpm until all the TRIOH is visually dissolved. Further, 2.02 mL of polycaprolactone-block-polytetrahydrofuran-block-polycaprolactone (Sigma-Aldrich, $M_n \sim 2,000$) (POLYOL) is added to pot B which will turn the solution viscous. Stir rapidly at 1000 rpm for 10 min or until POLYOL is visually dissolved in the solution. Transition of pot B mixture from a viscous state to considerably dilute state signifies the complete dilution of POLYOL in the mixture. Now add 1.136 mL of tolylene-2,4-diisocyanate (Sigma- Aldrich, 95%) (TDI) and further stir at 500 rpm for 5 min. Adding and mixing of all these precursors in pot B should yield a translucent solution. POLYOL and TDI should be preheated in the oven at 40°C for 30 min before adding them to the reaction mixture. Pot A containing the PMMA precursors is then vortex mixed for 2 min and directly poured into pot B. A clear transparent solution is obtained. A small amount (10 μL) of initiator dibutyltin dilaurate (Sigma-Aldrich, 95%) (DD) is then added to the reaction mixture followed by 0.01 v/v % of deionized water. Addition of water is essential to avoid the gelation of the PU PMMA IPN solution. The reaction mixture is then kept for 48 h at 60°C in an oil bath under darkness at a constant stirring rate of 500 rpm to obtain the final 80 mL batch of PU PMMA IPN colloid. Solvents acetone and xylene were both

treated with molecular sieves prior to carrying out the reaction to remove any absorbed moisture. All PU PMMA precursors are stored in the freezer prior to the reaction.

2.2 Synthesis of FS

To synthesize fluoro silica, 80 mL of dry chloroform (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99\%$), is first taken in a two necked round bottom flask which is then purged with nitrogen for 30 min to remove any atmospheric air. This is followed by the addition of 2 g of fumed silica nanoparticles (Sigma-Aldrich, 7 nm) under gentle stirring rate of 500 rpm. The reaction mixture is then further purged with nitrogen for 10 min followed by the addition of 0.945 mL of 1H,1H,2H,2H-perfluorooctyldimethylchlorosilane (Novachem). The reaction mixture is then kept for 48 h at 25 °C in an oil bath at a constant stirring rate of 500 rpm under nitrogen. After reaction completion, the mixture is poured equally into two 50 mL falcon tubes and chloroform is separated from the solid mass (wet fluoro silica) using the application of centrifugal force. The separated chloroform is decanted away and two further washings of the wet fluoro silica is carried out with more chloroform repeating the centrifuge step to get rid of any unreacted constituents. If the solid mass sticks to the bottom of the falcon tube, ultrasonication could be used to mix the chloroform and the solid mass before each washing cycle. After the final washing, the wet fluoro silica is left for drying at room temperature for 48 h. To form a sprayable solution the dried FS is re-suspended in acetone (Sigma-Aldrich, $\geq 99.5\%$) at a concentration of 25 mg mL⁻¹.

2.3 Fiber reinforced composites and spray coating

Carbon fiber reinforced composite sheets of CF-nylon (Cetex TC910, Tencate Advanced Composites), CF-PEEK (Pi preg #3085, Porcher Composites) and CF-epoxy (simple woven 1x1, Automated Manufacture of Advanced Composites, University of New South Wales) were all cut into 2.5 x 2.5 cm² pieces. The substrates were then spray coated with 3 ml of PU PMMA IPN per sample using handheld spray gun (nozzle diameter, 0.3 mm) from an effective working distance of 15 cm at a constant pressure of 3 bar. The IPN sprayed samples were then left to cure for 20 min before spraying the final layer of fluoro silica. For this interfacial layer, 3 ml of FS per sample was sprayed from a working distance of 10 cm at 3 bar constant pressure using a different but similar handheld spray gun. Curing of the IPN is essential for complete integration of sprayed fluoro silica particles into the polymer layer. The samples were then kept in drying oven at 35 °C for 3 h to ensure complete cure before carrying out any further testing.

2.4 Characterization

Surface analysis of the coated and uncoated composite materials was carried out using optical microscope (Nikon Eclipse E200, 5x magnification) and SEM (Zeiss UltraPlus analytical scanning electron microscope (FESEM) at 3kV). The samples were first sputter coated (Emitech K550X) with platinum for 90 s at 10 mA current before taking SEM images. Spectroscopic analysis was performed using fourier transform infrared spectroscopy in attenuated total reflectance mode (FTIR-ATR, diamond crystal, Bruker-Alpha, U.S.A) taking 24 scans in 400-4000 cm⁻¹ range to verify the successful functionalization of composite substrates with PU PMMA IPN and FS. Wetting analysis was carried out using Phoenix-MT (T) contact angle analyser (Surface Electro Optics, Republic of Korea). Moisture absorption was studied by submerging the coated and uncoated composite substrates under deionized water at a depth of 1 cm. Samples were taken out at 30 min interval for the first 3 h and weighed to check for an increase in mass due to water absorption before finally keeping them for 21 more hours to study the effect of 24 h submersion in total.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Fabrication of coatings and spectroscopic analysis

Automated fiber placement (AFP) is a widely used advanced composite fabrication technique [23]–[25]. A schematic of the manufacturing process for fiber reinforced composite materials using AFP

Figure 1: Schematic demonstrating the fabrication process of superhydrophobic coatings on fiber reinforced composites manufactured using automated fiber placement technique followed by sequential spray coating of PU PMMA IPN and FS to generate micro-nano roughness to achieve dewetting properties

Figure 2: Fourier transform infrared spectroscopic analysis of (a) CF-epoxy, (b) CF-nylon and (c) CF-PEEK samples. Blue line represents the uncoated substrates, orange line corresponds to the cured PU PMMA IPN layer, green line represents substrates with just the FS layer and red line represents sequential deposition of both PU PMMA IPN and FS particles.

followed by its sequential coating with PU PMMA IPN and FS to impart superhydrophobic property is depicted in figure 1. The PU PMMA colloid generates micro roughness and FS particles impart the necessary nano roughness, together forming a nano-micro hierarchical textured pattern on the surface of the substrate achieving the Cassie Baxter state. Spectroscopic analysis of the cured IPN coatings on CF-epoxy, CF-nylon and CF-PEEK confirms the successful formation of PU PMMA IPN. Complete

polymerization is indicated by the disappearance of 2235 cm^{-1} $\text{N}=\text{C}=\text{O}$ isocyanate stretch band corresponding to TDI and formation of 3300 cm^{-1} $-\text{NH}$ stretch band, see figure 2 (orange lines). Similarly, successful synthesis of the FS (green lines, figure 2) was confirmed from the peaks in the fingerprint region ($500\text{-}1500\text{ cm}^{-1}$) which correspond to the $-\text{CF}_2$ groups. The identical spectra for sequentially sprayed IPN and FS (red lines, figure 2) and FS only coatings confirm the successful formation of FS coating on top of the IPN layer.

Figure 3: Microscopic images (5x) of as received bare substrates (row 1), PU PMMA IPN coated substrates (row 2), FS only coating (row 3) and sequentially PU PMMA IPN – FS coated substrates (row 4). Columns represent the different composite materials: CF-epoxy (column 1), CF-nylon (column 2) and CF-PEEK (column 3).

3.2 Surface and wetting analysis of coatings

Microscopic images of the uncoated and coated substrates are shown in figure 3. Micro roughness generated by spraying the IPN can be visually observed on all coated samples (row 2, figure 3). Fluoro silica particles could also be clearly distinguished when the composite samples were coated with FS

Figure 4: SEM images of as received CF-PEEK substrate (row 1), with FS only coating (row 2) and with IPN and FS coating (row 3). Column 1 depicts images at 20 K X magnification and column 2 shows images at 100 K X magnification. Inset in image (c) demonstrates the superhydrophobic behavior of IPN and FS coated CF-PEEK sample.

only coating (row 3, figure 3). To analyze the IPN-FS sprayed samples, SEM images were taken on CF-PEEK substrate for FS only coating (row 2, figure 4) and IPN-FS sequentially sprayed coating (row 3, figure 4). Nano-micro textured pattern could distinctly be observed in IPN-FS coated sample. The FS only coating however appears to be a much smoother surface. Agglomerates of FS particles could also be clearly observed in higher magnification SEM images (100 K X, column 2, figure 4).

Analysis of contact angle measurements demonstrated successful fabrication of superhydrophobic state on all three substrates with contact angles measuring greater than 150° with almost 0° roll-off

angle. The best contact angle was obtained on CF-epoxy (165°) having an initial contact angle of 52° for the uncoated CF-epoxy sample. CF-PEEK demonstrated a contact angle of 160° as compared to 73° for its uncoated counterpart and for CF-nylon contact angle increased to 158° from 62° , see table 1.

Composite Material	Uncoated Contact Angle	IPN-FS Coated Contact Angle
CF-epoxy	52°	165°
CF-PEEK	73°	160°
CF-nylon	62°	158°

Table 1: Contact angle measurements for uncoated and IPN-FS coated carbon fiber composites

3.3 Analysis of moisture degradation

The IPN-FS sequentially sprayed samples showed a general trend of decreased water absorption in all three composite materials with maximum water absorption occurring in CF-epoxy followed by CF-nylon and the least amount of water absorption was noticed in CF-PEEK. In all three substrates, there was 21-60% reduction in water absorption when the substrates were coated with IPN-FS superhydrophobic coating with CF-PEEK showing the maximum reduction of absorbed water with 60% less increased mass as compared to uncoated CF-PEEK sample. The increase in mass of the coated substrates can be attributed to water seeping through the edges of the substrate. Although both faces of each sample was coated to provide maximum protection from moisture absorption, there was still water absorption observed due to the inherent difficulty of spraying method with coating edges of the sample. Other techniques could be investigated like dip coating to achieve better coverage of the substrate and avoid any uncovered areas to minimize water seeping through the edges, but this is out of scope of the present study.

Figure 5: Change in weight of coated (green lines) and uncoated (red lines) CF-epoxy (dash-dotted lines), CF-nylon (dotted lines) and CF-PEEK (dashed lines) after 24 h of water submersion

4 CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

Three different carbon fiber reinforced composite substrates were coated with superhydrophobicity imparting materials to prevent them from absorbing moisture and undergo degradation. The high contact angles and extremely low roll-off angles indicated the successful fabrication of Cassie Baxter

state. The substrates were then immersed in water for 24 h to study their water absorption. All coated substrates demonstrated reduced water absorption compared to their uncoated counterparts. Water absorption was still observed in coated samples which was attributed to water seeping through the edges which were difficult to coat with the current spraying technique. Alternate techniques could be investigated to fully cover the samples avoiding any leakages. A longer study could be carried extending from few weeks to months to study the prolonged effect of water immersion on coated and uncoated composite materials. The effect of water absorption on the thermal and mechanical properties of these polymer composites should also be investigated.

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. Gay, S. V. Hoa, and S. W. Tsai, *Composite Materials: Design and Applications*. CRC Press, 2002.
- [2] A. P. Mouritz, E. Gellert, P. Burchill, and K. Challis, "Review of advanced composite structures for naval ships and submarines," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 53, no. 1, pp. 21–42, 2001.
- [3] A. Grant, "Sporting composites," *Reinf. Plast.*, vol. 49, no. 5, pp. 46–49, 2005.
- [4] C. Soutis, "Fibre reinforced composites in aircraft construction," *Prog. Aerosp. Sci.*, vol. 41, no. 2, pp. 143–151, 2005.
- [5] K. Friedrich and A. A. Almajid, "Manufacturing aspects of advanced polymer composites for automotive applications," *Appl. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 20, no. 2, pp. 107–128, 2013.
- [6] H. Adam, "Carbon fibre in automotive applications," *Mater. Des.*, vol. 18, no. 4–6, pp. 349–355, 1997.
- [7] S. Ramakrishna, J. Mayer, E. Wintermantel, and K. W. Leong, "Biomedical applications of polymer-composite materials: a review," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 61, no. 9, pp. 1189–1224, 2001.
- [8] A. Zafar, F. Bertocco, J. Schjødt-Thomsen, and J. C. Rauhe, "Investigation of the long term effects of moisture on carbon fibre and epoxy matrix composites," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 72, no. 6, pp. 656–666, 2012.
- [9] G. Sala, "Composite degradation due to fluid absorption.pdf," vol. 31, pp. 357–373, 2000.
- [10] A. Kootsookos and A. P. Mouritz, "Seawater durability of glass- and carbon-polymer composites," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 64, no. 10–11, pp. 1503–1511, 2004.
- [11] R. Selzer and K. Friedrich, "Mechanical properties and failure behaviour of carbon fibre-reinforced polymer composites under the influence of moisture," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 28, no. 6, pp. 595–604, 1997.
- [12] B. F. Boukhoulida, E. Adda-Bedia, and K. Madani, "The effect of fiber orientation angle in composite materials on moisture absorption and material degradation after hygrothermal ageing," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 74, no. 4, pp. 406–418, 2006.
- [13] N. Sateesh, P. Sampath Rao, D. V. Ravishanker, and K. Satyanarayana, "Effect of Moisture on GFRP Composite Materials," *Mater. Today Proc.*, vol. 2, no. 4–5, pp. 2902–2908, 2015.
- [14] A. B. D. Cassie and S. Baxter, "Wettability of porous surfaces," *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, vol. 40, pp. 546–551, 1944.
- [15] W. Chen, A. Y. Fadeev, M. C. Hsieh, D. Öner, J. Youngblood, and T. J. McCarthy, "Ultrahydrophobic and ultralyophobic surfaces: some comments and examples," *Langmuir*, vol. 15, no. 10, pp. 3395–3399, 1999.
- [16] H. Li, J. Yang, P. Li, T. Lan, and L. Peng, "A facile method for preparation superhydrophobic paper with enhanced physical strength and moisture-proofing property," *Carbohydr. Polym.*, vol. 160, pp. 9–17, 2017.
- [17] T. Fei, H. Chen, and J. Lin, "Transparent superhydrophobic films possessing high thermal stability and improved moisture resistance from the deposition of MTMS-based aerogels,"

- Colloids Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.*, vol. 443, pp. 255–264, 2014.
- [18] S. O. Kwon, J. Kim, M. W. Moon, and C. H. Park, “Nanostructured superhydrophobic lyocell fabrics with asymmetric moisture absorbency: Moisture managing properties,” *Text. Res. J.*, vol. 87, no. 7, pp. 807–815, 2017.
- [19] Y. Qing, M. Liu, Y. Wu, S. Jia, S. Wang, and X. Li, “Investigation on stability and moisture absorption of superhydrophobic wood under alternating humidity and temperature conditions,” *Results Phys.*, vol. 7, pp. 1705–1711, 2017.
- [20] S. Muzenski, I. Flores-Vivian, and K. Sobolev, “Durability of superhydrophobic engineered cementitious composites,” *Constr. Build. Mater.*, vol. 81, pp. 291–297, 2015.
- [21] W. S. Y. Wong, Z. H. Stachurski, D. R. Nisbet, and A. Tricoli, “Ultra-durable and transparent self-cleaning surfaces by large-scale self-assembly of hierarchical interpenetrated polymer networks,” *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 8, no. 21, pp. 13615–13623, 2016.
- [22] S. A. Bird, D. Clary, K. C. Jajam, H. V Tippur, and M. L. Auad, “Synthesis and characterization of high performance, transparent interpenetrating polymer networks with polyurethane and poly (methyl methacrylate),” *Polym. Eng. Sci.*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 716–723, 2013.
- [23] G. Marsh, “Automating aerospace composites production with fibre placement,” *Reinf. Plast.*, vol. 55, no. 3, pp. 32–37, 2011.
- [24] D. H. J. A. Lukaszewicz, C. Ward, and K. D. Potter, “The engineering aspects of automated prepreg layup: History, present and future,” *Compos. Part B Eng.*, vol. 43, no. 3, pp. 997–1009, 2012.
- [25] J. Frketic, T. Dickens, and S. Ramakrishnan, “Automated manufacturing and processing of fiber-reinforced polymer (FRP) composites: An additive review of contemporary and modern techniques for advanced materials manufacturing,” *Addit. Manuf.*, vol. 14, pp. 69–86, 2017.